

Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy Compromising The Pros And Cons Of The Relationship Between Personality Traits And Entrepreneurial Success

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Personality Trait, IPIP Big Five Model, Entrepreneurial Self- Efficacy, Entrepreneurial Success</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5090790</p>	<p><i>This research aims to examine the effect of general Personality Traits on Entrepreneurial Success, alongside the potential and mechanism of the Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy in mediating their effects. Data were analyzed via multivariate Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) techniques to evaluate the four (4) hypotheses in the model, using second-order confirmatory tests. The results showed that Personality Traits significantly affects Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy, which also influences Entrepreneurial Success. Therefore, Personality Traits significantly affect Entrepreneurial Success through Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy. This research mediates the pros and cons of the relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Success. The research was conducted specifically on micro and small business actors while ignoring medium-sized businesses. Hence, further research is needed to examine the hypotheses on this population. The results can be applied to the world of education, especially in target planning, policy stipulation, and evaluation of the success of learning entrepreneurship. This research using a more comprehensive concept of Entrepreneurial Success.</i></p>

Introduction

The role of an entrepreneur in the economy is directly proportional to the professional risks, and common knowledge holds that not everyone can adapt and tolerate these risks. There is an undeniable empirical fact that MSME actors come from various groups, education levels, genders, economies, ethnicities, tribes, and demographics. These differences show that MSME actors do not suddenly appear but are dominated by external aspects. Therefore, entrepreneurship is considered an important social phenomenon and has become the object of scientific investigation in various rapidly growing fields, such as Anthropology, Geography, Psychology, Economics, Business, And Sociology (Barral et al., 2018; Jufri & Wirawan, 2018).

A question to be answered from cross-scientific collaboration in entrepreneurship research concerns the factors affecting entrepreneurial success. Consequently, academics and authors explore the deepest aspects of humans, namely personality traits, which is an individual's self-system about his perspective and environment and affects attitude and daily behavior. Since this context also affects their perspective on the entrepreneurial profession, associating personality traits with individual self-efficacy required to run a business is worth studying.

At this point, individuals are the focus due to the dominance difference between the founder or owner of MSEs and large companies pemilik (Rauch & Frese, 2000; Sidik, 2013). Meanwhile, an area of research with a strong tradition is the study of individuals and their relationship with entrepreneurship. Research related to this phenomenon underlines the dimensions of individual motivation and cognition concerning the creation of new ventures and entrepreneurship (Barral et al., 2018). The way individuals think and act as entrepreneurs has become an important question for many researchers, educators, and decision-makers in their efforts to promote the increased entrepreneurial activity of independent individuals and organizations. (Newman et al., 2019).

Associating personality with entrepreneurship, especially regarding survival and success, is controversial. Based on the history of this topic, research in the 70s and 80s neglected personality factors in entrepreneurship. The reasons were weak theorization and methodological qualities, inconsistent results, and the decreasing roles of founders and owners in business growth (Brandstätter, 1997). Although some research has succeeded in obtaining positive evidence about the relationship between MSE owners and business performance, the construction or variables with important roles in mediating them have not been properly clarified (Sidik, 2013). Also, the theory used in the model development of mediating variables is considered controversial (Rauch & Frese, 2000). Recently, this question became gradually answered, especially after Bandura introduced the concept of self-efficacy. This motivational construct has been shown to broadly affect individuals in determining activity, goal-setting, persistence, and performance (Newman et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2005).

Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy is a derivative of the self-efficacy concept and an individual's self-confidence in his ability to execute tasks related to entrepreneurship in marketing, management, risk-taking, etc.

To answer the questions above, many research has attempted to explore the factors affecting self-efficacy in entrepreneurship, such as education level, experience, gender, and so on (Newman et al., 2019). Meanwhile, a psychological approach was employed as the deepest aspect of the individual, which affects one's view of himself and his environment. This is considered as one of the factors affecting the emergence of self-efficacy in entrepreneurship, regardless of the education level, experience, gender, ethnicity, and other demographic aspects. Research on the effect of self-efficacy, specifically Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (ESE), on other variables, has been performed for the past two decades. Subsequently, the meta-analysis conducted by Newman et al., (2019) succeeded in identifying variables proven to be affected by ESE, one of which was Business Performance.

However, another problem was found while discussing Success, as it often overlaps with Business Performance. Research on Entrepreneurial Performance and Success is often represented by financial indicators and workforce growth, which is an avenue for concern. The reason is that some basic literature on individual motivation in undertaking the profession state that finance is only one of the many factors promoting individuals to become entrepreneurs. Other factors, such as individual freedom and social benefit, which are also motivations, have been rarely explored and discussed in previous studies, especially relating to Entrepreneurial Success (Hasan et al., 2020).

Also, research found that most entrepreneurs with non-economic goals do not intend to innovate or expand their operations but prefer to maintain their size and scope. Hence, these objectives are the driving force behind the start of new businesses. Meanwhile, Kuratko *et al.* used the term 'four structures of goal-setting factors,' which are extrinsic rewards, independence or autonomy, intrinsic rewards, and family security (Kerr et al., 2018). Gratefully, the importance of non-economic benefits is now well documented and quite strong in various literature amidst the confusion of goal-setting by entrepreneurs.

Theory and hypotheses

1. Relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy

Personality traits have been studied extensively to assess their effect on entrepreneurship. Meanwhile, the theory of career choice explains that an individual's career choice is an expression of his personality. Previous research also found a positive relationship between personality characteristics and entrepreneurial activities, including Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Newman et al., 2019; Rachmawan et al., 2015; Zhang & Cain, 2017; Zhao et al., 2005). Self-efficacy is a motivational construct shown to be a factor affecting individuals' choices in determining activity goals, persistence, and performance in various contexts.

Although the personality theory views vary widely, research in recent decades has moved on to the Big-Five definition. The Big-Five Personality Traits theory consists of extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness to experiences, and neuroticism. Previous studies found that personality traits are significantly associated with self-efficacy, and these findings were based on a genetic perspective arguing that they are hereditary (Wang et al., 2016).

H1: Personality Traits affect Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy

2. Relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Success

Research with the theme of the internal and external factors of Entrepreneurial Success has been conducted from over three decades ago until now. Personality traits are one of the factors thought to affect this Success, and previous research has shown that it supports individuals to become successful entrepreneurs. A person's personality trait is often empirically associated with the tendency and successful experience as an entrepreneur (Begley & Boyd, 1987; Brandstätter, 2011; Kerr et al., 2018; Schmitt-Rodermund, 2004; Viinikainen et al., 2017).

Hence, research with this theme in entrepreneurship is increasingly practiced based on the Big Five Personality Traits approach introduced by Digman in 1990 and popularized by McCrae and Costa. Although the results of these various research vary, they tend to agree on the O +, C +, E +, A-, N- patterns.

H2: Personality Traits affect Entrepreneurial Success.

3. Relationship between Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy and Entrepreneurial Success

Self-efficacy is a construct that drives an individual to act and has been shown as one of the factors affecting the choice of goals, persistence, and performance in various contexts (Rachmawan et al., 2015). This construct has been investigated extensively and is clearly presented in the literature that contributes significantly to performance in various fields. Subsequently, Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy is a broader concept of Self-Efficacy, which is a component that is inseparable from Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory. Meanwhile,

Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy was defined from various aspects, and Mcgee, Peterson, Mueller, & Sequeira, (2009) described it as an individual's belief in their potential to be successful in executing business activities. Conversely, Chen, Greene, & Crick (1998) and Segal, Borgia, & Schoenfeld, (2005) defined the construct as one's confidence in their capability and ability to succeed in the process of starting a business. A theoretical framework connecting self-efficacy, performance, and Entrepreneurial Success has been proposed concerning previous strong and abundant research and meta-analyses (Kerr et al., 2018; Newman et al., 2019; Oyeku et al., 2014). Consequently, several revealed a positive relationship between the level of self-efficacy and business performance (Herath et al., 2014; Lindsay et al., 2007), measured by income and/or workforce growth (Moyer, 2016), life satisfaction, and subjective happiness (Strobel et al., 2011).

H3: Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy affects Entrepreneurial Success.

H4: Personality Traits affect Entrepreneurial Success through Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy.

Method

The analytical method used was Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), which is very sensitive with regard to the number of samples, even in comparison to other multivariate analyses. Meanwhile, the data collection technique was a semi-open questionnaire, where the answer options were provided. However, regarding the sample identity, the research objects were still allowed to answer according to their wishes. Hence, the questionnaire related to the Personality Traits, Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy, and Entrepreneurial Success variables only provided answer options selected by the objects.

Sample

The population was micro and small business actors in Indonesia. They were determined using non-probabilistic sampling, specifically the purposive technique, where the sample specifications were determined as follows:

1. The age of SME actors should be 30 years old to ensure the personality traits were mature enough and the possibility to change was small, according to Costa & McCrae, (1994)
2. The SME actors employ a minimum of 3 employees, excluding the owner. Besides the determination of this number, besides being supported by the definition of MSEs by competent authorities (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2006), it also aims to minimize bias during the response to the Entrepreneurial Success instruments.
3. SMEs actors that had been in the profession in the last three years and this decision was based on the assumption that such business actors are quite comfortable with their profession and have witnessed their business performance. Therefore, instruments related to entrepreneurial success can be responded to properly.

The determination of the 502 samples considered the model complexity outlined by Hair et al., (2014) as follows, there were eight (8) constructs, one (1) was measured using two indicators, then there was one under-identified construct. Based on the considerations above, the sample size of 502 was an appropriate number as the primary data source. Therefore, the requirements and expert recommendations mentioned above can be fulfilled.

Variables

This section explains the limitation of terms or operational definitions contained in the research title. The purpose was to avoid misunderstandings and generate a similarity in perception between the author and the reader, to ensure both parties share the same meaning.

1. Personality Trait (PT), as a set of psychological characters and mechanisms within an organized individual, is a relatively enduring perspective that affects the interaction and adaptation of individuals in an environment. In this research, it refers to the Big Five Model, while the measurement instrument represents the IPIP Big-Five Factor Marker (IPIP-BFM) developed by (Goldberg, 1992). IPIP-BFM 50 is a model used in psychology to recognize the measurement of human personality through traits arranged in five domains formed using factor analysis. The five personality trait domains are Intellect, Emotional stability, Conscientiousness, Agreeableness, and Extraversion.

Personality Trait Instruments in Indonesia are quoted from Akhtar & Azwar, (2019) and published on the website www.IPIP.org.

2. Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (ESE) is an individual's belief in their potential to be successful in executing activities and becoming a business actor. ESE was evaluated using the five sub-dimensions by Chen et al., (1998), comprising Marketing, Innovating, Management, Risk-taking, and Financial control.

3. Entrepreneurial Success (ES) is an individual's understanding and assessment of the achievement criteria considered important by entrepreneurs (Wach et al., 2018). The dimensions and instruments of the Subjective Entrepreneurial Success-Important Scale are Firm performance, Workplace relationships, Personal fulfilment, Community impact, and Personal financial rewards (Wach et al., 2016).

Measurement

1) **Validity test** aimed to show the extent to which a measuring instrument can measure what is intended. The standard used in measuring convergence validity between each indicator and construct is the Standardized Regression Weights, with a value of 0.4, for interpretive purposes, regardless of sample size (Stevens, 2009). Some experts attribute the cut-off factor loading to the number of samples used in the research. Meanwhile, the factor loading of each indicator in a construct affects AVE, which is a measurement parameter for construct validity. Accordingly, the average value of the path coefficient squared (Average Variance Extracted) is expected to be large. Although the rule of thumb for the AVE value is >0.5 , 0.4 is accepted when the construct or composite reliability coefficient is greater than 0.6 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Hair et al., (2014) described the suitability of the sample number in determining the cut-off factor loading, which decreases as the sample increases.

Table 1 Factor Loading Values for Practical Significance

Factor Loading	Sample Size needed for significance
0.30	350
0.35	250
0.40	200
0.45	150
0.50	120
0.55	100
0.60	85
0.65	70
0.70	60
0.75	50

2) **Reliability test** was conducted to prove the accuracy, consistency, and precision of the instrument in measuring constructs. A way to measure reliability in CB-SEM is through Composite reliability, using Cronbach's Alpha. Although the most adapted cut-off coefficient of construct reliability is >0.7 (Hair et al., 2014), some argue that a value of 0.6 is acceptable (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988).

3) **Discriminant validity test** aimed to determine the difference in the research variables. It is performed because each variable in the model should be unique to facilitate their differentiation and prevent overlapping. A lower correlation value between constructs than the AVE square root means the variables can be distinguished or are unique from one another (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Some academics state that a value below 0.8 indicates discriminant validity between constructs (Kline, 2015).

Hence, the ideal standard acceptance of assumptions in measurement models at SEM is as follows:

Table 2 Standard Measurement Model Test

TEST	MEASUREMENTS	CUT OFF
<i>Convergence Validity</i>	<i>Factor Loading</i> <i>AVE</i>	> 0.4
<i>Construct Reliability</i>	<i>CR</i>	>0.6
<i>Discriminant Validity</i>	Correlation Value between constructs and AVE	$\sqrt{AVE} > r_{xy}$ Or $r < 0.8$

4) **Model Goodness of Fit/GoF** was conducted to evaluate the entire model, and even the essence of structural equation modelling analysis is an index of this test. Generally, the model goodness of fit is divided into three parts, namely Absolute, Incremental, and Parsimonious Fit Indices, each of which is explained by sub-indicators. Although many indicators exist, there is a disagreement among academics about the number and type of indices to be reported on the GoF test.

Hair et al., (2014) recommended using several model goodness fit index, including:

- a) The value of χ^2 and the index corresponding to df
- b) one absolute fit index (example: GFI, RMSEA, or SRMR)

- c) one incremental fit index (example: CFI or TLI)
- d) one goodness-of-fit index (example: GFI, CFI, TLI, etc.)
- e) one badness-of-fit index (example: RMSEA, SRMR, etc.)

Based on all previous opinions, the standard cut-off acceptance values of the model goodness of fit indices are as follows:

Table 3 *Goodness of Fit Standards*

INDEX	CUT-OFF
Absolute Fit Indices	
▸ CMIN/DF	≤3.00
▸ GFI	>0.9
▸ RMSEA	<0.08
▸ RMR	<0.08
▸ AIC	< AIC saturated and independent model
▸ CAIC	< CAIC saturated and independent model
▸ BCC	< BCC saturated and independent model
▸ BIC	< BIC saturated and independent model
▸ ECVI	< ECVI saturated and independent model
▸ MECVI	< MECVI saturated and independent model
Incremental Fit Indices	
▸ AGFI	≥0.90
▸ TLI	>0.90
▸ NFI	>0.90
▸ CFI	>0.90
▸ IFI	>0.90
▸ RFI	>0.90
Parsimonious Fit Indices	
▸ PRATIO	>0.06
▸ PNFI	>0.06
▸ PCFI	>0.06
▸ PGFI	>0.06

5) **Significance test** was conducted to determine the significance of the relationship between the model constructs then, the hypothesis testing was performed based on the measurement results. The basis for decision making in accepting and rejecting the hypothesis, with a maximum significance level of 5%, was to examine the probability level value on the regression weight table,

If $P > 0.05$ and $C.R < 1.96$, then H_1 is rejected and H_0 is accepted

If $P < 0.05$ and $C.R > 1.96$, then H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected

Subsequently, a formula developed by Sobel, (1982) was used to calculate the significance of the indirect and total effect between the research variables.

6) **R² (The Coefficient of determination)** was tested to determine the percentage of the variance of each endogenous variable described by exogenous variables. The path coefficients include direct, indirect, and total effects and the interpretation of the R² recommended by Latan, (2013) was 25%, 45%, 65%, representing weak, moderate, and strong, respectively.

the results of the research that has been done, namely: 1) Triangulation and 2) member check.

Results and Discussion

Table 4 Average Variant Extracted

			Factor Loading	R ²	1-R2	AVE	√AVE
X1	<---	PT	0.871	0.759	0.241	0.465	0.682
X2	<---	PT	0.487	0.237	0.763		
X3	<---	PT	0.759	0.576	0.424		
X4	<---	PT	0.693	0.480	0.520		
X5	<---	PT	0.524	0.275	0.725		
TOTAL			3.334	2.327	2.673	0.542	0.736
Y1	<---	ESE	0.852	0.726	0.274		
Y2	<---	ESE	0.744	0.554	0.446		
Y3	<---	ESE	0.798	0.637	0.363		
Y4	<---	ESE	0.553	0.306	0.694		
Y5	<---	ESE	0.699	0.489	0.511		
TOTAL			3.646	2.711	2.289	0.537	0.733
Z1	<---	ES	0.751	0.564	0.436		
Z2	<---	ES	0.668	0.446	0.554		
Z3	<---	ES	0.730	0.533	0.467		
Z4	<---	ES	0.697	0.486	0.514		
Z5	<---	ES	0.811	0.658	0.342		
TOTAL			3.657	2.687	2.313		

Table 5. Discriminant Validity Test

	PT	ESE	ES
PT	0.682		
ESE	0.482	0.736	
ES	0.404	0.625	0.733
	= √AVE		
	= r _{xy}		

Table 5.45 indicates that the three AVE square roots were much greater than the correlation of $r < 0.8$ between the constructs. Therefore, the variables in model I were unique.

Table 6 Goodness of Fit Model I

INDEX	CUT-OFF	RESULT	DESCRIPTION
Absolute Fit Indices			
CMIN/DF	< 3.00	2.170	Fit
GFI	>0.9	0.888	Marginal Fit
RMSEA	<0.08	0.057	Fit
RMR	<0.08	0.028	Fit
AIC	< AIC saturated and independent model	641,524 > 600,000	Marginal Fit
CAIC	< CAIC saturated and independent model	914,990 < 2064,997	Fit
BCC	< BCC saturated and independent model	649,932 > 645,045	Marginal Fit
BIC	< BIC saturated and independent model	858,990 < 1764,997	Fit
ECVI	< ECVI saturated and independent model	1.792 > 1.676	Marginal Fit
MECVI	< MECVI saturated and independent model	1.815 > 1.802	Marginal Fit
Incremental Fit Indices			
AGFI	≥ 0.9	0.862	Marginal Fit
TLI	>0.9	0.890	Marginal Fit
NFI	>0.9	0.835	Marginal Fit
Table 5.47 continuation			
CFI	>0.9	0.903	Fit
IFI	>0.9	0.904	Fit
RFI	>0.9	0.813	Marginal Fit
Parsimonious Fit Indices			
PRATIO	>0.6	0.884	Fit
PNFI	>0.6	0.738	Fit
PCFI	>0.6	0.798	Fit
PGFI	>0.6	0.722	Fit

1) Hypothesis test

The second stage was the structural parameter estimate test to evaluate the relationship between the constructs, and the hypothesis testing was performed based on the results of the parameter measurement. Subsequently, the basis for accepting or rejecting this hypothesis, at a maximum confidence level of 5%, was to examine the probability level (p-value) and Critical Ratio (C.R. value), which are identical to the z-value on the regression weight table. The criteria for hypothesis acceptance are as follows:

- If $P > 0.05$ and $C.R. < 1.96$, then H_1 is rejected, and H_0 is accepted
- If $P < 0.05$ and $C.R. > 1.96$, then H_1 is accepted, and H_0 is rejected

To calculate the significance of the indirect I effects between the variables, a formula developed by Sobel (1982) was used:

$$z = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{(b^2 SE_a^2) + (a^2 SE_b^2)}}$$

The results of the parameter estimates' testing for the research model are as follows:

Table 7 Hypothesis Testing 1-3

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Description
ESE	<---	PT	.562	.090	6.209	***	Significant
ES	<---	ESE	.462	.057	8.036	***	Significant
ES	<---	PT	.128	.066	1.940	0.052	Insignificant

Table 8 Recapitulation of Effect between Variables

Variable	Effect		
	Direct (a)	Indirect (b)	Total (a+b)
PT (X) → ESE (Y)	0.482*	-	0.482
ESE (Y) → ES (Z)	0.560*		0.560
PT (X) → ES (Z)	0.134	0.482 x 0.560 = 0.270*	0.404

*Significant 1%

According to Table 8, there were three significant relationships, all significant variables were at the 1% level. Consequently, the following calculations were used to determine to extent to which the exogenous variables explained the percentage variance of each endogenous variable:

$$R^2 \text{ of Variable Y} = \beta_{YX_n} \cdot r_{YX_n}$$

$$R^2 \text{ of Variable partial Z} = \beta_{ZX_n} \cdot r_{ZX_n} \text{ dan } \beta_{ZY_n} \cdot r_{ZY_n}$$

$$R^2 \text{ of Variable simultaneous Z} = \beta_{ZX_n} \cdot r_{ZX_n} + \beta_{ZY_n} \cdot r_{ZY_n}$$

Table 9 Squared Multiple Correlations Model I

VARIABLE	r	β	R ²
PT → ESE	0.482	0.482*	23.3%
PT → ES	0.404	0.134	5.4%
ESE → ES	0.625	0.560*	35.0%
PT & ESE → ES			40.4%

* sig. 1%

The Personality Traits (X) variable was built by five dimensions, and each was explained by several indicators. Subsequently, the effect of Personality Traits (X) on Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy (Y) was 0.233 or 23.3%, while the remaining 77.7% were affected by other external variables. Conversely, 40.4% of the Entrepreneurial Success variable (Z) was explained by the two exogenous variables, namely Personality Traits (X) and Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Y), while the remaining 59.6% was affected by other variables outside the research.

The discussion is grouped into three (3) parts, where the first explains the effect of Personality Traits (X) on Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Y), and the second discusses the effect of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Y) on Entrepreneurial Success (Z). Then, the last section discusses the effect of Personality Traits (X) on Entrepreneurial Success (Z), either directly or mediated by Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Y).

1. The Effect of Personality Traits on Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy

Personality traits have been studied extensively to assess their effect on entrepreneurship. The Career Choice, Fit, and Person-Environment (P-E) theories explain that an individual's career choice is an expression of his personality. Although personality theory views vary widely, research has moved on to the Big-Five definition in recent decades. The Big-Five personality traits theory consists of extroversion (Extraversion), agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness to experiences (intellect), and neuroticism (emotional stability).

Previous research found a positive relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Activities, including Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Newman et al., 2019; Obschonka & Stuetzer, 2017; Rachmawan et al., 2015; Zhang & Cain, 2017; Zhao et al., 2005). Subsequently, Personality Traits (X) were shown to affect Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Y) by 23.3% at a 99% confidence level.

Although the magnitude of this effect was interpreted as weak, the high level of confidence cannot be ignored. This means that almost one-quarter (¼) of a person's confidence and self-efficacy in performing entrepreneurial activities were explained by Personality Traits. The weak but significant effect is very natural, considering that the concept of Self-Efficacy is the result of interactions between individuals, cognitive, and social environments. Therefore, Personality Traits solely having a dominant effect on entrepreneurial confidence and trust would be unnatural.

2. The Effect of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy on Entrepreneurial Success

A theoretical framework linking self-efficacy, entrepreneurial performance, and success in entrepreneurship has

been robustly and abundantly proposed in several previous research and meta-analyses (Kerr et al., 2018; Newman et al., 2019; Oyeku et al., 2014). These various researches showed that Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Y) has a significant positive effect on Entrepreneurial Success (Z) at a 99% confidence level, with a path coefficient of 0.560.

Consequently, the strong effect of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy on Entrepreneurial Success obtained in this research is not new, as it has been previously confirmed by many previous studies. Also, several studies have revealed a positive relationship between the level of Self-Efficacy on business performance (Herath et al., 2014; Lindsay et al., 2007). The measurement parameters were growth in income and workforce (Moyer, 2016), life satisfaction, and subjective happiness. (Strobel et al., 2011). A positive and significant effect of ESE on Intrinsic Entrepreneurial Success was also shown (Jumain et al., 2017).

Self-Efficacy is a construct promoting an individual to act and is a factor affecting an individual's choice of goals, persistence, and performance in various (Rachmawan et al., 2015). Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy is a derivative of this broader concept and a component that is inseparable from Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory.

3. The Effect of Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy on Entrepreneurial Success

Research with the theme of internal and external factors affecting entrepreneurial success has been conducted from over three decades ago until now, and personality traits are one of the factors thought to affect this success. The Career Choice, Fit, and Person-Environment (P-E) theories also explain that an individual's career choice is an expression of his personality. Meanwhile, this personality is often empirically associated with the tendency to become a successful entrepreneur (Begley & Boyd, 1987; Brandstätter, 2011; Kerr et al., 2018; Schmitt-Rodermund, 2004; Viinikainen et al., 2017).

Previous research has shown that personality traits support the success of individuals as entrepreneurs. However, Rauch & Frese, (2007) noted that the results of this effect on success are polarized in two. These are a positive relationship (Barrick & Mount, 1991; Boz & Ergeneli, 2014; Brandstätter, 2011; Ciavarella et al., 2004; Leutner et al., 2014; Obschonka & Stuetzer, 2017; Rauch & Frese, 2000; Schmitt-Rodermund, 2004), or no relationship (Brockhaus & Horwitz, 1986; Gartner, 1989; Low & MacMillan, 1988).

Based on the year and examining the two groups of results above, both research that rejected the relationship was performed in the early period before the 1990s. However, those that stated otherwise were conducted after. Subsequently, this research discovered that Personality Traits (X) has a positive but insignificant effect on Entrepreneurial Success (Z) at the 5% confidence level. However, relaxing the level to 10% produced a significant effect, with a low correlation coefficient, namely 0.134, and this result seemed to accommodate the two groups of previous research.

This research also confirmed that the relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Success is weak, according to the group that rejected this assumption. Nevertheless, tests showed a significance that cannot be ignored, meaning that although the relationship is weak, positive and significant personality traits can promote entrepreneurial success. Therefore, the group that assumed a relationship between these two variables was not wrong.

Likewise, this research also revealed that the presence of Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy (Y) as a moderating variable further strengthens the effect of Personality Traits (X) on Entrepreneurial Success (Z). Without mediation by the Z variable, the regression coefficient X against Y had a value of 0.134, which increased to 0.270 with a mediating effect at the 99% confidence level. Furthermore, these exogenous variables (PT and ESE) were proven simultaneously to explain entrepreneurial success at a score of 40.4%, while the remaining 59.6% were affected by other variables outside the research. This value is not considered small, as many external variables, such as education, skills, economic situation, and other social environments, which are also strongly suspected of affecting success, especially in entrepreneurship, were not examined. Therefore, 40.4% as the value for the physiological factors that affect entrepreneurial success cannot be ignored.

Conclusion

Literature that aims to determine the effect of Personality Traits on Entrepreneurial Success mediated by Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy is rare and almost not found. Although the supporting literature for this research was quite abundant, the novelty obtained was the success in clarifying the interaction and effect of genetic and social factors on performance. Meanwhile, Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy are part of the psychological aspect but are different and can be distinguished. Hence, where the dominant personality traits are affected by genetics, self-efficacy is very much controlled by social interactions, and both have been shown to affect entrepreneurial performance in different ways.

The results also succeeded in mediating the differences in research opinions, alongside the mechanisms and stages relating to the effect of Personality Traits on Entrepreneurial Success. This research expressly explained that Personality Traits do not directly promote Entrepreneurial Success but act through Entrepreneurial Self-

Efficacy. Furthermore, Self-Efficacy is a psychological construct affected by genetics, as well as an individual's social interactions in life. Therefore, insisting on connecting Personality Traits to Entrepreneurial Success without any intermediate variables is inappropriate, as the results will be biased and inconclusive.

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